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Evaluate The Effectiveness of Planned Teaching Programme on Knowledge Regarding Breast Self-Examination Among The Selected Women (18-50 Years) in Rural Area at Masturi-Bilaspur Chhattisgarh

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Abstract :

A quasi experimental, one group pre- and post-test research design was used to evaluate the effectiveness of Planned Teaching Programme on knowledge regarding Breast Self-Examination (BSE) among the selected women (18-50 years) in rural area at Masturi- Bilaspur (C.G). Non probability convenience sampling technique used to select 40 women (18-50 years). The data was collected by using self prepared questionnaires before and after the PTP. The findings was revealed that there was a statistically significant difference

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between the pre test and post test knowledge level ($t = 26.04$) at, $p < 0.0001$ level depicting that the PTP was effective in improving the knowledge of women regarding BSE. Conclusion: The nurses, who play an important role in BSE education, can be taught in a variety of settings - either in one-to-one basis or in a group for early detection of breast related problems women.

Keywords : Planned Teaching Programme (PTP), Breast Self Examination (BSE), knowledge and women

Introduction :

“A feminine women has the effects of sunrise on man’s soul”

The Breast plays a significant role in women sexuality, sense of femininity, beauty, self-identity and motherhood^(1, 2). A breast disorder, whether benign or malignant, can cause more anxiety and fear of potential disfigurement, loss of sexual attractiveness and even death^(2, 3). The breast cancer is now the most common cancer in the majority cities of India and account for 10% of all breast problems⁽⁴⁾. In equally male and female benign lesion of breast occur more frequently, the malignant lesions account for 70-30% out of that 99 percent occur in female, 75% of cancer come about after 40 years of age, less than 20% occurs at less than 30 years⁽⁵⁾. One woman is diagnosed as breast cancer in every 4 minutes and dies in every 8 minutes.

Breast cancer normally is detected either during a screening examination, before symptoms have developed, or after symptoms have developed, when a woman feels a lump, distortions or swelling^(6, 7) and it is a preventable cancer which increases the chances of survival, reduces mortality rate and improves patient prognosis. Early detection plays a crucial role for breast cancer and the BSE increases breast health awareness of women^(8, 9).

Breast self examination is inexpensive, safe and non invasive method of screening tool in diagnosis breast cancer at early stage and it can be done at home⁽¹⁰⁾. It is important to remember that everyone’s breast are different and that can be related to aging, menstrual cycle, pregnancy and menopause^(7, 11, 12). The best time to perform breast self-examination is about 3-5 days after the menstrual period

starts when the breast tissue is no longer swollen or tender from hormone elevations. The literature reports that the percentage of women performing monthly BSE is less than 15% although they are aware of its importance⁽¹³⁾. In most developing countries breast self examination is the only feasible approach to mass population coverage for a longtime⁽⁵⁾. Breast awareness is the best way to go⁽¹⁴⁾. India need to reach the achievement and it is only possible with preparation and prevention of screening, awareness and proper treatment. The nurse play a important role in creating awareness regarding breast related problem by education. Breast Self- Examination, a modality used for the early detection of breast cancer⁽²⁾.

Statement of the problem :

“A study to evaluate the effectiveness of Planned Teaching Programme on knowledge regarding Breast Self-Examination among selected women (18-50 years) in rural area at Masturi- Bilaspur (C.G)”.

Objectives :

- To assess the existing knowledge regarding Breast Self- Examination among the women.
- To evaluate the effectiveness of Planned Teaching Programme on knowledge regarding Breast Self- Examination among the women.
- To find the association between the pretest knowledge level regarding Breast Self- Examination among the women with selected demographic variables.

Hypotheses :

- There is a significant difference between pretest and posttest knowledge score among the women regarding BSE.
- There is a significant association between the pretest knowledge levels regarding Breast Self- Examination among women with selected demographic variables.

Research Methodology :

A quantitative research approach with quasi experimental one group pre test and post test research design was adopted for the study. 40 women (15-50 years) in rural areas of Masturi-Chhattisgarh were selected by non probability convenient sampling technique. The data was collected by self prepared questionnaires which were designed by the researcher and the content validity was obtained from the experts of obstetric and gynecological nursing and OBG doctor, Community Health Nursing, Child Health Nursing and Medical and Surgical Nursing.

The tool used for the study was organized into two sections. Section A: consists of demographic variables and section B: consist of Self prepared questionnaires with 25 multiple choice questions. After obtaining permission from the concerned authorities to conduct the study, the informed consent from women was obtained and the data was collected.

The pre test was conducted on day 1 by using self prepared questionnaires; this was followed by planned teaching program and post test was conducted after 1 week by using same questionnaires. Collected data was analyzed by using descriptive statistic (percentage, mean and standard deviation) and inferential statistic ('t' test and chi square test).

Result and discussion :

In this study majority of women 19(47.5%) were between the age group of 36-45 years and 100% of women were belong to Hindu. Nearly 1/3 of women 36(90%) were working under daily wages and only 4(10%) were working in government sector. 25(62.5%) were educated up to secondary school level and 13(32.5%) were educated up to primary school level. 21(52%) were having 2 living children 16(40%) women were having 3 children and only 1 having more than 3 children. None of the mother was having family medical history. More than half of the woman 23(57.5%) were having Rs.1000-5000/ monthly family income.

Discussion based on the objectives :

- *The first objective was to assess the existing knowledge regarding Breast Self- Examination among the women.*

Table - 1 : Frequency and percentage distribution of pre test knowledge score regarding BSE among the women $n = 40$

S.No	Knowledge Level	Pretest	
		Frequency	%
1	Poor knowledge	26	65%
2	Average knowledge	13	32.5%
3	Good knowledge	01	2.5%

Table - 1 shows that 26(65%) of women had poor knowledge, 13(32.5%) of women had average knowledge and only 1(2.5%) of women had good knowledge regarding BSE.

- *The second objective of the study was to evaluate the effectiveness of Planned Teaching Programme regarding Breast Self- Examination among the women.*

Table - 2 : Mean and Standard Deviation of pre- and post-test knowledge score among women

	Mean	SD	Paired “t” Value	Effectiveness by ‘p’ Value
Pretest	7.8	19.5	26.04	$p < 0.0001$ HS Highly significant difference in mean pretest score and mean posttest score, showing effectiveness of teaching programme
Posttest	18.75	1.822		

Table - 2 shows that, the mean and standard deviation pre test knowledge score was 7.8 ± 19.5 whereas the post test mean and standard deviation score was 18.75 ± 1.822 . The calculated “t” value is 26.04 shows that the p value ($p < 0.0001$) is statistically highly significant in the post test compare to the pre test. Therefore it was inferred that the PTP is effective in increasing the knowledge level among the women. **The first Hypothesis (H₁)** shows significant difference between the pre test and post test score. So the hypothesis (H₁) was accepted.

Donmez Y.C, Dolgun. E. and Yavuz. M. (2012) was conducted a cross-sectional and descriptive study was aimed to evaluate women breast self-examination (BSE) practice and effects of a planned educational programme for breast cancer and BSE. The samples of the study were consisted 266 women. The study data were collected by a questionnaire in six months periods as two times in a month in which the periods were defined and announced to all women. After that all the women were informed about BSE. The statue of performing BSE of women ($n = 146$) was evaluated. They were interviewed on phone after 6 months. The average age of women was 35.68 ± 7.54 . It is also determined that (61.3%) had no knowledge about BSE, (87.6%) had examined clinical breast examination (CBE) in a year and half of them (50.8%) never practiced BSE, (29.0%) had BSE regularly every month. Concerning the status of BSE practice before the education and after the education significant difference is found statistically ($p < 0.00$) the significant of the study is that it is to give education about breast cancer and BSE for raising awareness among women⁽¹⁵⁾.

- *The third objectives of the study was to find the association between the pre test knowledge level regarding Breast Self- Examination among the women with selected demographic variables.*

Table - 3 : Association between pre test knowledge score with selected demographic variables

Sl No.	Areas	Chi square	Level of significances
1.	Age	18.22(12.838)	$p < 0.005$ HS
2.	Education	8.865(7.82)	$p < 0.02$ HS
3.	Income	6.08(5.99)	$p < 0.05$ significant
4.	No. of Living Children	2.009(7.82)	$p > 0.05$ NS

Table - 3 reveals that there is an association between pretest knowledge score with some selected demographic variables like age, education and income. **The second hypothesis (H₂)**, there is a significant association between the pretest knowledge score with age, education and income. Therefore the second hypothesis was accepted.

Conclusion :

The study result showed that Planned Teaching Programme regarding BSE was effective in enhancing knowledge level of the women. Majority of the women in the posttest had good knowledge score and some had average knowledge score when compare to the pretest knowledge score. These findings will help the nurses who play an important role in BSE education, which can be taught in a variety of settings-either in one-to-one basis or in a group for early detection of breast related problems women.

Implication :

Nursing Practice :

Nurses and health visitors can initiate health education programme regarding Breast Self-Examination among the women for at least twice a year. They can instruct them to do it in their home setting regularly.

Nursing education :

The result of this study emphasis the learners to utilize the knowledge of breast self- examination both in hospital and community setting in order to early diagnosis of breast related problem.

Nursing Research :

This research finding can be used as evidence based for providing knowledge among the women & men regarding Breast Self-Examination.

Nursing Administration :

This study can helps the administrator in organizing continuous nursing education programme, in service education, job training programme for the nurses.

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